

**METHOD OF TEACHING STUDENTS OF ADVANCED CLASSES
ENGLISH THROUGH THE METHOD OF GAMES.**

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Abstract: This article describes the importance of using gaming technology in English lessons in elementary school. Because the games motivate people to learn a foreign language and influence all aspects of their development: senses, consciousness, will and behavior.

Keywords: foreign languages, games, teaching methods, primary school

First, let's get acquainted with the pun. what is the game A game is a structured activity, usually done for fun and sometimes used as an educational tool? Games are distinct from work, which is usually done for reward, and art, which is more concerned with the expression of ideas. Key components of games are objectives, rules, challenge, and interaction. Games generally involve mental or physical stimulation, and often both. Many games help develop practical skills, serve as a form of practice, or otherwise serve an educational, simulated, or psychological role. Games can be used at any stage of the lesson once the target language has been introduced and explained. They serve both as an exercise in memory and review, as well as a way to use the language freely, and as a means to an end rather than an end in itself. They can also serve as a diagnostic tool for the teacher, who can identify difficulties and take appropriate corrective action. Games are fun and kids love to play them. That alone is a strong argument for including them in EFL classes. Play is an important and natural part of growing up and learning. Through play, children experiment, discover and interact with their environment.

Many experienced authors of textbooks and method manuals have argued that games are not just time-consuming activities but have great educational value. WR Lee believes that most language games encourage learners to use the language instead of thinking about learning the correct forms. He also says that games should be at the heart of language teaching programs, not secondary. Richard Amato sees it similarly, warning against overlooking the pedagogical value of games, especially in foreign language classes. Using the games has many advantages. Games can reduce anxiety and make acquisition of input more likely (Richard - Amato). They are extremely motivating and entertaining and can give shy students more opportunities to express their opinions and feelings. They also allow learners to gain new experiences in a foreign language that are not always possible in normal classrooms. In addition, to quote Richard Amato, they add variety to regular classroom activities, breaking the ice but also being used to introduce new ideas.

Further support comes from Zdybiewska, who believes that games are a good way to practice language as they provide a model of what learners will use the language for in real life in the future. Games stimulate, entertain and promote the flow of language. If not for any of these reasons, they should be used simply because they help students see beauty in a foreign language and not just problems. [1, 12] Games are often used as a quick warm-up or when there is some time left at the end of the lesson. However, as Lee notes, a game should not be viewed as a sideline that fills in the occasional moment when the teacher and class have nothing better to do. Games should be at the heart of foreign language teaching. Rixons suggests using games in all phases of the lesson, provided they are appropriate and carefully chosen.

At different stages of the lesson, the teacher goals associated with a game may vary:

1. Presentation. Provide a good model that makes its meaning clear;
2. Controlled practice. Elicit good imitation of the new language and appropriate responses;
3. communicative practice. Give students the opportunity to use the language. [2, 24]

Games are also good for review practice and help learners retain material in an enjoyable and fun way.

Elementary school classroom games work best when they build on the premise of relaxation and reward, but actually reinforce skills already learned. Once the teacher has figured out which game works best, the effective teacher can use that game to keep students engaged and focused. Many teachers use fun and educational games in their classes to increase student activity, which is the main method of acquiring solid knowledge, skills and abilities. Didactic games are one of the most important means of intellectual and moral education of children. The main form of didactic entertainment is games that create a stable interest in learning and relieve tension. They form psychological qualities necessary for the educational process, such as thinking, attention and memory. They also form the competences of the pedagogical work. All game plans can be divided into: 1. Educational games based on study materials; 2. entertaining games characterized by puzzles, logic games, speed games. [1, 46] The game plan in elementary school is first explained in terms of the psychological and educational characteristics of younger children. The special importance of play lies in its role as a means of adapting children to learning. Therefore, it must become an integral part of the educational process in primary schools.

The cognitive character development game sphere is used to develop logical thinking, imagination and quick learning. There are some entertaining games like jigsaw puzzles, crosswords, riddles, riddles, games with geometric figures and others. These games aren't about speed; it's about finding the right solution. These games promote the development of constructive thinking, train the skills of creative types, and develop spatial thinking. As the experience of teachers working with the game curriculum shows, teachers can quickly increase the effectiveness of teaching by organizing the process of cognitive character formation in the form of games.

There are many great games to play in the elementary school classroom. It's just a matter of finding the few games that certain students actually enjoy and actively

participate in when played. Elementary school students love games because it feels like a break from everyday rudimentary learning, but that's just an excuse. Many of the best games played are actually based on concepts that are explored. This is the advantage of playing within the confines of the elementary school classroom. Games should be positive in every moment they are applied as this will lead the students to enjoy the activity while having a hidden useful exercise. And hidden is mentioned because these types of activities usually make students forget that they are learning and focus more on playing and/or winning. [3, 18] Games that are designed as exercises in the classroom with play equipment and situations can motivate and encourage students to take pedagogical action. The main areas in which game methods and techniques are used: 1) didactic goal for students in the form of a game task; 2) training activities according to the rules of the game; 3) The training material is used as a tool in learning activities, didactic tasks are introduced as a competitive element during the game; 4) the successful implementation of didactic tasks related to the outcome of the game. [4, 54] Gaming technologies are one of the most effective forms of education for younger students in the classroom, allowing teachers to make students' work interesting and exciting, not only on the creative and exploratory level, but also in everyday learning. The place and role of game technology in the educational process, a combination of game and learning elements, depends on the understanding of the teacher's functions and the classification of educational games. G. K. Selevko classified educational games according to the following criteria: field of activity, type of pedagogical process, game technique, specialty, game environment.

There can be the following groups of games:

- 1) education, training, monitoring and summary;
- 2) informative, educational, sociable;
- 3) reproductive, productive, creative;
- 4) communicative, diagnostic, psychological, etc.

Thus, Gaming Technology can be understood as including a sufficiently large

group of methods and techniques for organizing the educational process and a variety of educational games that will help you make the learning process fun and interesting. Much of this is important in developing the creative skills of junior year students. From the variety of educational games, the teacher should choose the one that most accurately conveys the content of the study material to interested students and is a catalyst for the development of students' creative abilities. [5, 124] Experience has shown that the successful development of children's creative abilities should provide the solution to educational problems. It forms the important characteristics such as: the positive attitude towards school, a school subject; the ability and willingness to participate in the collective training activities; the ability to listen to each other; voluntary desire to expand their abilities; disclosure of one's own creative abilities; self-expression, self-assertion. These qualities arouse the interest of elementary school students and the desire to continue their activities and contribute to the development of creative abilities. Games in language classes help children see English learning as enjoyable and rewarding. Playing games in the classroom develops the ability to cooperate, compete without being aggressive. Most importantly, games can facilitate lesson planning.

All English lessons must include games as games are best built through demonstrations rather than lengthy explanations. Play is the most important and essential element in the development of man or society as a whole. This is how children discover the world while playing. The need to play and the desire to play must be properly used and directed with a view to solving specific problems in the educational process. Play will be the means of education and teaching if it is included in the whole pedagogical process. When the teacher directs the game and organizes the life of the students in the game, she influences the development of the students from all sides: meaning, consciousness, will and behavior.

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